

Final Report on Reproducing the Paper "Multi-Emotion Detection in User-Generated Reviews" by Buitinck et al. (published in line with ECIR'15)

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to reproduce the supervised multi-emotion detection experiment carried out by Buitinck et al. 2015 based on textual data stemming from 44 Hollywood movie reviews [1]. The training and test dataset provided by Buitinck et al. are used as a basis for recreating the experiment, which compares the One-vs.-Rest (OvR) classifier and the Random k -labelsets (RAKEL) algorithm according to the F_1 score as the main performance metric [1]. Reproducibility of the project was not given out of the box based on the available paper and train/test split. Indeed, a number of decisions had to be made with regard to the choice of algorithm implementations and versions (in Python's *scikit-learn* library), the related tuning parameters and methods as well as the implementations of the significance tests. All in all, this paper achieves to reproduce the structure and workflows of the experiment. However, differences in the actual outcome can be observed given the series of assumptions that had to be made due to the lack of clear specification by the authors of the original paper.

KEYWORDS

Multi-label classification, multi-emotion detection, RAKEL, OvR, random k -labelset classifier, one-vs.-rest classifier, binary relevance reduction, affective computing

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, the reproducibility of Buitinck et al.'s piece of work "Multi-Emotion Detection in User-Generated Reviews" is explored, their experiment is reproduced, and observations in line with the reproduction workflow are analyzed.

Chapter 2 gives an overview on the experimental set-up in the underlying paper by Buitinck et al., which was published in 2015. The reasoning behind their selection of algorithms (at a high level) and steps indicated to carry out the experiment are illustrated. Additionally, the dataset and preprocessing steps / code provided are introduced.

In chapter 3, our strategy and the necessary workflow steps to reproduce the results of the underlying paper by Buitinck et al. are described in greater detail. This includes information on the preprocessing steps, the algorithm / significance test versions and implementations, on how to go through the workflows steps of the experiment being recreated.

In chapter 4, we discuss the difficulties that we encountered during the reproduction process with regard to reproducibility. The original paper left several key aspects open, which were then subject to analysis and investigation from our side. Thus, the reasons why these aspects matter and the impact that making assumptions on those aspects might have on the results are described. We then compare our experimental set-up and our reproduced results with the insights we have on the set-up and the results

from the original paper. We evaluate to what extent the information given in the original paper is sufficient to reproduce the results. We compare the results of the significance test in the original with the reproduced version in order to find out whether the latter reveals the same clues on significance (with respect to p -values), and whether the results of the original paper can be confirmed by our elaboration or not.

In chapter 5 we conclude on our findings in line with our efforts to reproduce the experiment from the original paper.

2 OVERVIEW OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP IN THE UNDERLYING PAPER

In contrast to the majority of research in conventional "affective computing", the paper by Buitinck et al. does not only dedicate to detecting one emotion for each sentence, but rather explores the problem of supervised, simultaneous multi-emotion detection based on textual data [1]. The authors also refer to it as multi-label classification, with the labels to predict being seven emotions (i.e. *anger*, *fear*, *interest*, *joy*, *love*, *sadness*, *surprise*) and in addition the *none* label [1]. The underlying textual data stems from 44 reviews of Hollywood movies across several genres [1]. The two chosen multi-label classification algorithms are applied to sentence-level data (comprising a total of 629 sentences) of the reviews complemented with a set of zero to seven emotions [1]. The number of sentences used in this experiment, which is in the dimension of a few hundreds, is considered much smaller in comparison to previous research in this area, which used at least ten times larger samples to run the algorithms [1]. The authors provide the review data in the necessary structure for analysis as well as the code for separating the observations into training and test dataset in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/NLeSC/spudisc-emotion-classification> [1]. The full dataset is split into 80% training data and 20% test data [1].

As for the multi-label classification algorithms, the authors compare the One-vs.-Rest Classification (also called Binary Relevance Reduction) algorithm with the Random k -labelsets (in short RAKEL) algorithm [1]. They indicate that a bag-of-words (BOW) transformation is used to process the movie review sentences (which were still in natural language formulation after in the raw form) more conveniently [1]. Within this step, they claim to perform "stop word removal and optional *tf-idf* (i.e. term frequency-inverse document frequency) weighting" as well [1]. At this point, *tf-idf* denotes a statistical measure to determine the relevance or importance of a specific word in the collection examined. However, at this point it is not clear whether they applied this step within both algorithm runs in the same way. Basically, both algorithms are expected to simplify the multi-label task to a "binary or multi-class learning" task, which can use linear support vector machines (SVMs) as base learners [1].

As already mentioned, the **One-vs.-Rest Classification Algorithm (or Binary Relevance Reduction)** serves to reduce a " k -way multi-label classification problem to k independent support vector machines" [13] [1]. In doing so, the SVMs are enabled to make a distinction between one label (i.e. in this case one emotion) and all the other labels [13]. This classification method enables the tuning of each one of the SVMs in a stand-alone manner,

which in turn contributes to finding an optimal model for each label compared to the rest [1]. The downside of this procedure is that information on the label dependencies is not exploited in such a setting [1]. Buitinck et al. selected the F_1 score based on five-fold stratified cross-validation (CV) on the training data as the performance metric to optimize [1]. With a view to optimizing the classifier into this direction, the authors suggest to optimize the parameters (or "settings" as they call it) of each SVM separately [1]. Among those settings to tune for each label, they mention grid search with parameter value of 0.1, 1, 10, 100 or 1000, linear or logarithmic tf , tf or $tf-idf$, and oversampling or not [1]. The final choice of parameters is made based on "experience with other text classification problems" (which is not explained any further) according to the authors [1].

Likewise, the **Random k -labelsets (RAKEL) algorithm** tackles the multi-label classification problem. For this experiment, the authors look at RAKEL algorithm with linear SVMs as its "base learners" and fixed label subset size of $k=3$ [1]. RAKEL is essentially based on the idea of the label powerset method, but avoids that the calculation grows into an exponential-sized problem of the latter [1]. Instead, RAKEL solves multi-label classification in an ensemble fashion by creating and training "(randomly chosen without replacement) label powerset classifiers on a fixed-size label subset" [1]. By the means of a voting phase, the algorithm determines into which category each observation is classified [1]. In line with tuning, the authors opt for " $tf-idf$ weighting with logarithmic tf , automatic oversampling, and a fixed regularization parameter of 1 for all SVMs" [1].

By **comparing the two algorithms**, the authors take the tuned One-vs.-Rest classifier as a baseline, which is subject to benchmarking against the RAKEL classifier (based on the movie review dataset), with the latter being the more technically advanced algorithm [1]. The F_1 score (per label and total average across all labels) is seen as the main performance metric, which is reported as "an average over ten runs of each training algorithm" [1]. Additionally, the accuracy in terms of "one minus Hamming Loss" is indicated [1] [4].

Figure 1 below depicts the results of Buitinck et al.'s benchmarking of the two algorithms [1]. With the F_1 score being the main performance criterion to examine, the overall result reveals that the RAKEL algorithm led to a statistically at $\alpha = 0.05$ level significant, better F_1 score [1]. The absolute difference is, however, not very large [1]. The authors ascribe this outcome to the fact that the not so advanced One-vs.-Rest classifier was tuned extensively [1]. Furthermore, the RAKEL algorithm produced the result much faster than the One-vs.-Rest algorithm due to the lengthy tuning phase of the latter [1]. The One-vs.-Rest algorithm performs badly on the "Anger" label, but RAKEL performs even worse on that emotion as it fails to predict this emotion, whose meaning is typically conferred in a paraphrased way in textual reviews.

	Algorithm/performance metric			
	OvR accuracy	OvR F_1 score	RAKEL acc.	RAKEL F_1
Anger	.940 ± .018	.105 ± .129 [△]	.937	.000
Fear	.910 ± .015	.267 ± .039	.921	.546 [▲]
Interest	.802 ± .000	.359 ± .000 [▲]	.818	.343
Joy	.939 ± .005	.494 ± .056	.929	.471
Love	.706 ± .000	.626 ± .000 [▲]	.675	.586
Sadness	.849 ± .000	.296 ± .000	.905	.400
Surprise	.740 ± .051	.231 ± .029	.794	.278 [▲]
Overall	.841 ± .007	.432 ± .008	.854	.456 [▲]

Figure 1: Performance comparison based on F_1 score as well as accuracy, and significance test results based on Welch's one-sided t-test on the differences in F_1 score [1]. White triangle: significant at 0.001 level. Black triangle: significant at 0.05 level.

3 STRATEGY / WORKFLOW STEPS TO REPRODUCE THE RESULTS AND KEY FINDINGS

In line with reproducing the experiment of Buitinck et al., we used Python as the main programming language as well. Our project integrates the training and test data in the respective format, which the original authors provided in the aforementioned GitHub repository (see <https://github.com/NLeSC/spudisc-emotion-classification>). We use Docker to run the experiments in a more stable way and make the code more conveniently reusable. The base image is Debian Buster with Python Version 3.8.7 so that further reproduction efforts based on our project can start from a unified version. Further version information is indicated in the *requirements* text files. The information on how to run the project is provided in the *README* Markdown file. The results (i.e. F_1 score, accuracy scores, and p-values for the significance tests) we generate are written into the *output* directory in CSV as well as text format.

Our experiment is carried out by executing the *run_experiments.py* Python file. As the data provided in the original authors' GitHub repository is still in natural language form, and they mentioned further bag-of-words preprocessing including $tf-idf$ weighting, we added a transformer code part, which is used to carry out this preprocessing step [3]. Stop words removal was not considered as the information given by Buitinck et al. was insufficient to reconstruct the steps. More precisely, *CountVectorizer*, *TfidfTransformer* and *MultiLabelBinarizer* from *scikit-learn* (in short *sklearn*) library serve to create an appropriate pipeline to transform the data into binarized format for applying the multi-label classification algorithms. Essentially, $tf-idf$ weighting and logarithmic tf can either be switched on or off in any combination. In our implementation of the experiment, we set these parameters in a way to mimic the preprocessing parameter settings indicated in the original paper (see [1] [3]).

With regard to the implementation of the two algorithms, Buitinck et al. linked a paper by Pedregosa et al. with reference to their use of algorithms from *scikit-learn* (see [6]), but without indicating exactly what version, implementation or parameters they used. Based on this statement from the side of the authors, we selected the algorithms for the reproduction from Python's *scikit-learn* library. As Buitinck et al. do not provide any concrete information on which version, implementation or tuning they actually selected for their experiment, our choice of algorithms (which later on implied specific tuning parameter settings) may have an impact in terms of deviation of our reproduced results in comparison to the original paper.

For reproducing the results of the One-vs.-Rest (OvR) classifier, we chose *sklearn.multiclass.OneVsRestClassifier*, which obtains its input in preprocessed form by the means of the multi-label binarizer mentioned above [10]. According to the *sklearn* documentation, this multi-label classification method is also called One-vs.-All classifier [10]. Similar to the implementation in the original paper, we train one OvR (i.e. binary) classifier per emotion, and for each of the classifiers "fit the class against all other classes" [10]. As a base classifier, we use linear SVM from *sklearn* (*sklearn.svm.LinearSVC*) [9] with a random seed value. In line with parameter tuning, we explore the parameter settings mentioned in the original paper, namely: grid search with parameter $c \in \{0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000\}$, L_1 or L_2 regularization, linear or logarithmic tf , tf or $tf-idf$, oversampling minority class per sub-problem or not. The selection of these tuning criteria as well as the choice of their parameter values was largely not determined by Buitinck et al., who claimed to base their own choice on "experience with other text classification problems" [1]. Hence, the tuning phase could have a crucial influence on the results of our reproduction workflow [1].

For the implementation of the Random k -labelsets (RAKEL) algorithm, we considered *skmultilearn.ensemble.RakelD*, which also receives the preprocessed input similar to the OvR classifier [11] [14]. The chosen method

splits the "label space into equal partitions of size k and trains a label power-set classifier per partition" [14]. The result is calculated via summation of all the individual results [14]. As a base classifier, we chose linear SVM from *sklearn* (more precisely *sklearn.svm.LinearSVC*) with the same random seed value as for the OvR classifier, with regularization parameter $c=1$ as indicated in the original paper [9]. We set the label set size parameter to $k=3$.

Subsequently, we run both algorithms on the described fully preprocessed training dataset to fit the respective classifiers. Using the fitted classifiers, we make predictions for the test dataset. Based on the prediction results and the available labels of the test dataset, we calculate the performance metrics, i.e. the F_1 score and the accuracy. For the F_1 score, the usual method of calculation of *sklearn.metrics.f1_score* is chosen [7]. For the accuracy score, we use the Jaccard score from *sklearn.metrics.jaccard_score* [8]. This assumption is taken according to research by Gouk et al., who stated that "in multi-label classification performance metrics like the Jaccard index between two label sets" are used to measure accuracy [5]. Just like it was given in the original paper, we use the F_1 score as our main performance metric [1]. Table 1 below depicts the average F_1 and Accuracy scores (over ten runs) per label (excl. the "None" category) and overall for the One-vs.-Rest algorithm and the RAKEL algorithm for our best reproduction results using a simple OvR model with fixed parameters (i.e. linear SVM with L1 regularization, dual *false*, *tf-idf*, and without grid search per label). What Buitinck et al. concluded about predicting the emotion "Anger" can be confirmed. Indeed, the algorithms experience difficulties with forecasting it, which is probably due to the fact that criticism and anger are often expressed in an indirect way, so that they are not easy to grasp mathematically from the bag-of-words features for the algorithms, but would rather need to analyze connotation, indirect meaning, and semantics [1]. Table 3 indicates the parameters that were chosen in line with tuning for each emotion. Balanced class weight is used for all SVM. The same overall issues and trends apply for the model using flexible parameters incl. grid search, the results of which can be seen from Table 3. Table 3 shows that in this model, the OvR classifier is worse than in the fixed parameter model. Our outcomes show that the results from the original paper could not be fully reproduced with a view to the exact values, probably due to the missing information on algorithm versions / implementations, tuning parameters and strategies. Our results comparing the accuracy confirm Buitinck et al.'s results overall, and the results for F_1 score are close. According to our analysis, the accuracy of the RAKEL algorithm is slightly higher than the accuracy for the OvR algorithm, whereas the F_1 score of the OvR algorithm is slightly higher than the corresponding values for the RAKEL algorithm.

Table 2 illustrates the variance of the performance metrics calculated for the OvR and the RAKEL algorithms (for the fixed parameter model). It can be seen that the overall variance of the OvR algorithm is zero, whereas the overall variance of the RAKEL algorithm outcomes is non-zero (but close to zero). The variance of the performance metrics was not published for both algorithms by Buitinck et al. in their paper. Still, we consider it a useful complement to the mean scores. For completeness of the comparison, Table 5 represents the variance of the model with flexible parameters, but does not identify much difference between the two models.

Calculating execution times of the algorithms yielded an average of 0.035 seconds for the OvR algorithm compared to an average of 0.060 seconds for the RAKEL algorithm (across ten runs each) in the fixed parameter setting. This outcome does not fully confirm the results of the original paper, which claimed that the OvR algorithm took several minutes to execute [1]. In the flexible parameter setting, the OvR algorithm with an execution time of about 0.109 seconds is slower than the RAKEL algorithm which takes around 0.066 seconds. This confirms the time-related results by the original authors. Still, our implementation and tuning of it appear to be generally much faster than that.

Emotion	OvR F_1 (Avg.)	Ovr Acc.	RAKEL F_1	RAKEL Acc.
Anger	0.235	0.133	0.000	0.000
Fear	0.222	0.125	0.214	0.124
Interest	0.314	0.186	0.300	0.177
Joy	0.125	0.067	0.426	0.273
Love	0.400	0.250	0.602	0.431
Sadness	0.308	0.182	0.036	0.020
Surprise	0.277	0.160	0.244	0.141
Overall	0.269	0.158	0.260	0.167

Table 1: Model with fixed parameters: Average performance metrics (F_1 , Accuracy) per label and overall for the OvR and the RAKEL algorithm

Emotion	OvR F_1 (Vars.)	Ovr Acc.	RAKEL F_1	RAKEL Acc.
Anger	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fear	0.000	0.000	0.013	0.004
Interest	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.001
Joy	0.001	0.001	0.007	0.003
Love	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
Sadness	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Surprise	0.000	0.000	0.008	0.003
Overall	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.002

Table 2: Model with fixed parameters: Variance of performance metrics (F_1 , Accuracy) per label and overall for the OvR and the RAKEL algorithm

Emotion	c	Penalty	tf sublinear	tf use idf
Anger	1.0	L1	True	True
Fear	0.1	L2	False	False
Interest	0.1	L2	True	True
Joy	100.0	L1	False	True
Love	0.1	L2	True	True
Sadness	0.1	L2	False	False
Surprise	1.0	L1	False	False

Table 3: Model with flexible parameters: chosen parameters per label for SVC in the OvR algorithm

After the evaluation of the two algorithms performance according to the selected metrics, we test whether the differences in the F_1 score (i.e. the main performance criterion) is statistically significant. We apply the Welch one-sided t-test to the performance data points, similar to what is suggested in the original paper [1]. The Welch t-test tests on the difference in means without requiring the assumption of equal (population) variances [12]. As Buitinck et al. do not indicate any particular implementation or version of the Welch t-test. Hence, we chose the t-test from *SciPy*, i.e. *scipy.stats.ttest_ind* for this purpose, *scipyTTest*. The resulting p-values of the model with fixed parameters are depicted in Table 6, and the p-values of the model with flexible parameters in Table 7.

Emotion	OvR F1 (Avs.)	Ovr Acc.	RAKEL F1	RAKEL Acc.
Anger	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fear	0.167	0.091	0.214	0.124
Interest	0.091	0.048	0.300	0.177
Joy	0.364	0.222	0.426	0.273
Love	0.600	0.429	0.602	0.431
Sadness	0.000	0.000	0.036	0.167
Surprise	0.000	0.000	0.244	0.141
Overall	0.174	0.113	0.260	0.167

Table 4: Model with flexible parameters: Average performance metrics (F₁, Accuracy) per label and overall for the OvR and the RAKEL algorithm

Emotion	OvR F1 (Vars.)	Ovr Acc.	RAKEL F1	RAKEL Acc.
Anger	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fear	0.000	0.000	0.011	0.000
Interest	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
Joy	0.000	0.001	0.007	0.004
Love	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
None	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.001
Sadness	0.000	0.000	0.006	0.002
Surprise	0.000	0.000	0.005	0.002
Overall	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.002

Table 5: Model with flexible parameters: Variance of performance metrics (F₁, Accuracy) per label and overall for the OvR and the RAKEL algorithm

	F ₁	Accuracy
p-values		
Anger	0.000	0.000
Fear	0.407	0.478
Interest	0.057	0.060
Joy	1.000	1.000
Love	1.000	1.000
Sadness	0.000	0.000
Surprise	0.096	0.114

Table 6: Model with fixed parameters: p-Values resulting from Welch’s 1-sided t-test with respect to the differences in F₁ and Accuracy per label between the OvR and the RAKEL algorithms

Overall, the main workflows and calculations from the underlying paper can be reproduced. However, the findings that the authors emphasized cannot be confirmed, notably due to too many unclear aspects and insufficient information on the construction of the experiment where choices have to be made without concrete guidance stemming from the original paper. Obtaining the details on the tuning strategy for both of the algorithms would be crucial to improve the reproducibility of the experiment. Also, information on the implementation and version thereof for the algorithms would be essential in the reproduction process. We do not consider this a

	F ₁	Accuracy
p-values		
Anger	NaN	NaN
Fear	0.903	0.909
Interest	1.000	1.000
Joy	0.979	0.982
Love	0.571	0.595
Sadness	0.916	0.916
Surprise	1.000	1.000

Table 7: Model with flexible parameters: p-Values resulting from Welch’s 1-sided t-test with respect to the differences in F₁ and Accuracy per label between the OvR and the RAKEL algorithms

flaw in the technical set-up, but a lack of specification, which could rather easily be fixed by providing either the preprocessing code or the missing details (e.g. concerning used versions, implementations, preprocessing steps, experience on parameter tuning from previous projects) to fully reconstruct the experiment.

4 ENCOUNTERED DIFFICULTIES WITH REGARD TO REPRODUCIBILITY

With regard to reproducibility, the experiment and its results were at first neither executable nor reproducible out of the box. Even though we managed to find a way to reproduce the whole experiment as well as the results components (although with differences to the original authors’ results), it has to be said that only a very small part of the total code necessary to reproduce the experiment was available. We took this available part as a starting point for our reproduction workflows. Then we analyzed the paper thoroughly and recreated it step by step, which included taking a number of decisions on how to recreate the respective parts, as many steps were not described in the paper.

The basis for our reproduction work constituted the GitHub repository that Buitinck et al. referenced in their paper. We made use of the annotated movie review dataset and the Python code to generate the training and test dataset. The difficulty in progressing further based on these resources was that the train-test split was not the whole preprocessing workflow necessary to run the algorithms and reconstruct the experiment. Indeed, it was only a very small part of the preprocessing phase. Thus, we essentially had to recreate based on the paper’s section on preprocessing, which is not comprehensive, and just mentions the "standard bag-of-words features with stop word removal and optional *tf-idf* weighting" as preprocessing steps [1]. To us, this description appeared to be too short and vague to exactly reveal how to reconstruct this preprocessing step. Additionally, this description lacked detailed information on whether the data has to be prepared in the same way for both algorithms. Therefore, at a later step, we made the assumption that we base the algorithms on data preprocessed in a similar way. Apart from that, no information was indicated by Buitinck et al. on the implementation and version of preprocessing steps to transform the underlying movie review data from natural language format into binarized format.

As Buitinck et al. mentioned that they used Python’s *scikit-learn* library for their project, we also decided to program all parts of our project as far as possible with the help of algorithms and methods from this library. However, it was not clear from the paper whether the authors used *scikit-learn* for all preprocessing, modeling, performance evaluation, and tuning steps. When it comes to the base learners for the multi-label classification methods, Buitinck et al. referred to a paper by Pedregosa et al., which was

published in 2011, and suggested linear SVMs as base classifiers [1]. Given that we used the current version of the linear SVM implemented in Python, there might be differences to the algorithm that Buitinck et al. selected.

With respect to the One-vs.-Rest algorithm, the original authors suggested to tune it according to the best setting selected out of grid search with several specified parameters, either L_1 or L_2 regularization, either linear or logarithmic tf , either tf or $tf-idf$, and either oversampling or no oversampling [1]. But shortly after explaining this, they claim that they tuned the algorithms' parameter settings "based on experience with other text classification problems" [1]. We experienced difficulties at this point in the reconstruction process because Buitinck et al. did not provide information on what this "experience" actually meant in terms of concrete tuned parameter values or order of tuning them. Neither did they refer to any of their previous papers or projects in which they might have used tuning strategies for the multi-label classification algorithms under concern. "Automated oversampling of minority classes" is mentioned in the paper, but the authors do not mention how it is implemented, and external research on this topic was not usable straight away. We explored several options, among them ensemble-based methods and the MLSMOTE (Multilabel Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique), which was detailed in papers for instance by Charté et al. in 2015/16, and adds synthetically created observations to imbalanced datasets [2]. The underlying paper lacks guidance on which oversampling algorithm is used. So, this fact definitely had an impact on our results, and thus the degree of precision of the reproduced version. Apart from these difficulties, a different list of steps to tune the OvR classifier is given shortly afterwards in the original paper. So, it was again difficult for us to decide on what criteria to finally select for appropriate tuning of the algorithms, and how to carry it out.

Concerning the RAKEL algorithm, Buitinck et al. stated that they did "not apply the same tuning measures as for the One-vs.-Rest" algorithm due to performance reasons [1]. They presented $tf-idf$ weighting with logarithmic tf , automated oversampling, and a regularization parameter of 1 as the tuning settings [1]. Still, no information was given what implementation or version to do so was exactly used.

When it comes to the execution times of the two algorithms, Buitinck et al. claimed that the RAKEL algorithm was "notably faster than the OvR" algorithm, whereby the latter took several minutes to execute [1]. We encountered difficulties with regard to this because no details were given by the authors on the version or implementation, what tuning strategy they chose, and what environment / operating system they had selected to run the algorithms. We can just add at this point that in our reproduced experiment, both algorithms were fast, but the OvR algorithm was around twice as fast as the RAKEL algorithm in the fixed parameter setting. In the setting with flexible parameters, the OvR algorithm was around 40% slower than the RAKEL algorithm.

Finally, with a view to the results, Buitinck et al. stated "accuracy" as their second observed performance metric [1]. They did not mention any further details on the "accuracy" calculation. However, further research we carried out on the topic of performance in multi-label classification revealed that there is no single, unique definition of "accuracy" in this field of research [5]. Instead, for instance Gouk et al. suggested that the "accuracy" can among others comprise the Jaccard score or other similarity indexes [1]. Thus, we considered it difficult to find out what kind of "accuracy" score was actually calculated in line with Buitinck et al.'s paper.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper makes an effort to reproduce the multi-emotion detection experiment that Buitinck et al. carried out. Even though we succeeded in reproducing the overall experiment, we encountered several difficulties in line with recreating the workflows and steps for the experiment. We think that identifying these areas could help the original authors to make their work more transparent and more easily reproducible for the worldwide

research community in the information retrieval domain. We noticed that only the underlying dataset and a small part of the code of the preprocessing phase were made publicly available. Those given elements were executable, but the whole experiment as such was not executable out of the box. Instead, the largest part of the experiment had to be programmed anew by us in order to reproduce the results. The remaining preprocessing code as well as the implementation, evaluation and comparison of the algorithms were reproducible in their foundations based on information from the paper. But the guidance from the paper could not be put into practice as detailed as we aimed to follow it, since at many places in the explanations decisions of the original authors were either based on their experience or merely described at a high level so that it was difficult to reconstruct the exact chosen values, tuning strategies, algorithm implementations / versions, and execution environment. All in all, our version of the experiment reproduces the workflows, steps, and the results as such, but since a series of details, which would be necessary to reconstruct the experiment as precisely as possible, have not been mentioned in the original paper, our reproduced version does not confirm all exact conclusions and values.

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